

Call for contributions to:

FAT STS: a zine

Fat people experience substantial marginalization, due in large part to scientific rationalization. In opposition, fat liberation is a social movement aimed at dismantling anti-fatness: a form of discrimination which has been explored by fat studies scholars in other fields, but has received limited attention from science and technology studies (STS) researchers.

In response to this, we invite contributions from STS scholars, Society for Social Studies of Science (4S) community members, and researchers and activists interested in advancing fat liberation in science and technology to contribute to *FAT STS: a zine*, a submission to the [4S2025 conference](#).

We will welcome submissions—or provocations—of any form, so long as they:

- Can be printed on a 8.5x5.5 inch page
- Comply with our Contributor Community Standard (see below).

Submissions could include (but are not limited to) a statement of interest, a position paper, a research summary, or a showcase of artistic practice. We invite participants to consider the following topics for their submissions, but would be happy to be surprised by something different:

- Reflections on lived fat experience and STS
- Tensions between STS and Fat Liberation
- Journeys to supporting fat people in STS
- Fat activist research and design practices
- Anti-fatness and intersectionality
- STS and Fat joy

How to contribute

Submit using [this form](#) by 31 July 2025.

Submissions will be reviewed by the Zine editors:

LAURA CARTER, University of California, Berkeley, United States of America

ANKOLIKA DE, Pennsylvania State University, United States of America

REBECCA JONAS, University of California, Santa Cruz, United States of America

DAISY O'NEILL, Eindhoven University of Technology & Philips Experience Design, The Netherlands

BLAKELEY H. PAYNE, University of Colorado Boulder, United States of America

AISHA SOBEY, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom

JORDAN TAYLOR, Carnegie Mellon University, United States of America

We will accept as many submissions as we can reasonably put in a zine :) In the event that we are overwhelmed by submissions, we will select works based on their thematic cohesion, relevance to STS studies and originality. If we receive an overwhelming number of submissions, we will endeavour to create additional zines following the 4S conference to include all submitted work. Please indicate on your submission if you would be happy for your work to be included in a later edition!

Publication

Fat STS: a zine has been accepted to the refereed track of the 4S2025 Zine Festival. This means that 2–5 copies will be available in print at the conference (3–6 September 2025 in Seattle), and a digital version will be compiled in online proceedings, to be hosted on the 4S website.

Zines have a long tradition in fat liberation studies, and we intend to also submit the zine to the [Fat Liberation Archive](#) as a way to build connections between fat studies scholars, STS scholars, and fat liberation activists. (If you are looking for inspiration, please check out the FLA: other sources of inspiration include the [Queer Zine Archive Project](#), the works of Dr Charlotte Cooper, and places you can find by searching “[your location] zine library”.)

We will also make two versions available online through [Zenodo](#) (one formatted to read online, and one formatted to be printed out at home and distributed). These versions will list all the editors and contributors (except those who would prefer to be anonymised) in the metadata. They will be licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0). We encourage contributors, allies and fans to join in zine traditions by making their own copies on their home or office printers and giving them to friends, colleagues, co-conspirators, and local zine libraries.

Contributor Community Standard

Editors and contributors to *Fat STS: a zine* pledge to make participation in this zine project a harassment-free experience for everyone, regardless of age, body size, visible or invisible disability, ethnicity, sex characteristics, gender identity and expression, level of experience, education, socio-economic status, nationality, personal appearance, race, caste, color, religion, or sexual identity and orientation.

We pledge to act and interact in ways that contribute to an open, welcoming, diverse, inclusive, and healthy community.

Examples of unacceptable behavior by project members include derogatory comments or personal attacks, trolling, public or private harassment, disclosing personal information without permission, insults, or other unprofessional conduct.

Editors of this zine project have the right and responsibility to reject contributions that are not aligned to this Code of Conduct, and will communicate reasons for rejection decisions when appropriate.

(adapted from the [Contributor Covenant](#))